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A Critique On The Right Of The Nigerian Inmates To Dignity Of Human Person: A Need For Compliance

Tamunoemi A. Abbiyesuku*

***LL.B (Hons), LL.M (RSU), BL (Abuja), Ph.D Research Candidate (RSU),**

**Senior Lecturer, Department of Law,
School of Legal Studies,**

**Port Harcourt Polytechnic, Rumuola, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.
tamunoemi.abbiyesuku@portharcourtpoly.edu.ng, 08037632537.**

ABSTRACT

The incarceration of the Nigerian inmates does not in any form deprive them of the basic rights necessary for their wellbeing. Despite their confinement as a result of custodial judgement of being in conflict with the law, they are entitled to certain basic rights which are not in conflict with the penological objectives of the Nigerian criminal justice system. This article critiques the right of the Nigerian inmates to the dignity of human person and the need for compliance with the legal instruments protecting the right to the dignity of human person. The right to a befitting accommodation, bed/bedding and clothing which are the derivatives of the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person were examined. The principal aim of this article is to critique the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person, and make a case for reform, while the specific objective is to identify those rights which are implicit in the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person and make a call on the Nigerian authorities for compliance with the legal framework. The doctrinal research methodology was adopted and reliance was made extensively on primary and secondary sources of information, with the utilization of domestic, regional and international legal instruments, including case laws, among others. This article finds that the right of the Nigerian inmates to the dignity of human person has been contravened in several areas, such as harassment, verbal intimidation, chaining, solitary confinement, dehumanizing torture and so on. This article finds further that the Nigerian inmates rights to a befitting accommodation, bed/bedding, clothing and so on have been violated in several ways, such as non-provision of a befitting accommodation, bed/bedding, clothing, among others. This article concluded that the Nigerian authorities, particularly, the Nigerian Correctional Service, National Human Rights Commission, Legal Aid Council of Nigeria among others, are endowed with the responsibility of the protection of these rights, and therefore should take steps in ensuring the protection of the Nigerian inmates' rights to dignity of human person and to continue to ensure the curtailment of further violations of these rights. Therefore, this article recommends that the Nigerian Correctional Service should treat the Nigerian inmates with measures that conforms with their rights to dignity of human person guaranteed under the Nigerian Constitution, Nigerian Correctional Service Act, Anti-Torture Act, Robben Island Guidelines and Measure for the prohibition and Prevention of Torture, Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment in Africa, Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, United Nations Standard Minimum Rule, among others.

Keywords: Rights, Inmates, Dignity, Befitting Accommodation, Bed/Beddings, Clothing.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian inmates are persons, weather convicted or awaiting trial lawfully committed to custody for being in contradiction with the law as a result of custodial judgement.¹ The inmates in Nigeria are persons incarcerated in correctional centres serving correctional terms or unconvicted persons awaiting trial. The inmates include persons who are in lawful detention facilities, other than correctional centres. The setting is not limited to correctional centres, but can include community settings, such as work release programmes, probation, parole and so on.² The inmates in Nigeria are generally persons whose liberty has been restricted by the decision of the penological or criminal justice system of Nigeria.

The confinement of the Nigeria inmates in Nigerian correctional centres do not in any circumstances diminish their basic rights, including the right to dignity of human person, which are not in conflict with the Nigerian penological system. Kekere, posits that, ‘These individuals continue to be human beings and irrespective of the fact that they are in conflict with the law, they deserve human treatment that acknowledges and reaffirms, in the first place, their dignity and worth’.³ The Kampala Declaration on Prison Condition in Africa stipulates that inmates, ‘should retain all rights which are not expressly taken away by the fact of detention’.⁴ Again, the United Nation Human Rights Committee in its General Comment No. 21 aver that, ‘respect for the dignity of persons deprived of their liberty must be guaranteed under same conditions as for that of free persons ... such person shall enjoy all rights set forth in the covenant, subject to the restrictions that are unavoidable in a closed environment’.⁵ Moreso, the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights in its Resolution 19(xviii) 95 on Prisons in Africa, has it that the rights established and guaranteed under the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights extends to all categories of persons, including inmates, detainees and other persons deprived of the liberty.⁶

Accordingly, the inmates in Nigeria are entitled to right to Dignity of human person protected under the relevant laws,⁷ with its derivatives components of the right to a befitting accommodation,⁸ bed/beddings⁹ and clothing.¹⁰ This article therefore critique the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person with a view of calling on the Nigerian authorities, particularly, the Nigerian Correctional Service for compliance.

2.0 Right to Dignity of Human Person

The right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person is core to the whole idea of inmates rights, as respect for dignity of human person is the basis upon which acceptable standard of treatment is meted out to human beings.¹¹ The right to dignity of human person is a right which prohibits torture, inhuman

¹ Nigerian Correctional Service Act 2019, s 46.

² L O Gostin and Others (eds), *Ethical Consideration for Research Involving Prisoners* (National Academics Press 2007) 1.

³ A I Kekere, ‘The Rights of Detained and Condemned Prisoners in the Nigerian Correctional Facilities: A Synopsis of the Legislative Framework’ [2021](9)(1) *Journal of Law and Criminal Justice*, 6.

⁴ Kampala Declaration of Prison Condition in Africa 1996, para 2.

⁵ UN Human Rights Committee, ‘General Comment No. 21: Humane Treatment of Persons Deprived of Liberty - GC/10/04/1992’ <<https://www.ohchr.org>> accessed 15 February, 2026.

⁶ ACommHPR, ‘Resolution 19(xviii) 95 on Prisons in Africa’ <<https://www.achpr.org/doc.res/>> accessed 15 February, 2026.

⁷ Constitution of the Federal Republic Nigeria 1999 (as amended) ss 34(1), 17(2)(b); NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1).

⁸ NCSA (n1) ss 4(2)(a), 9(1)(b), 30(3).

⁹ *Ibid*, ss 9(i)(b), 30(3).

¹⁰ *Ibid*, s 30(3).

¹¹ A O Adekunle, ‘Human Rights on Death Row’ in A Ayua (ed), *Nigeria Current Legal Problems* (Nigeria Institute of Advanced Legal Studies 2000) 143.

and degrading treatment.¹² Thus one of the most basic tenets of modern international human rights law is the prohibition against torture, or other forms of cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.¹³ Accordingly, the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person is protected under the Nigerian Constitution,¹⁴ Nigerian Correctional Service Act,¹⁵ Administration of Criminal Justice Act,¹⁶ Anti-Torture Act¹⁷ and African Charter.¹⁸

Thus, Section 34(1) of the CFRN adumbrates that, ‘every individual is entitled to respect for the dignity of his person’, including the inmates in Nigeria. Accordingly, no person shall be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment, or beheld in slavery or servitude, or be required to perform forced or compulsory labour.¹⁹ Moreover, Section 17(2)(b) of the CFRN avers that, ‘the sanctity of the human person shall be recognized and human dignity shall be maintained and enhanced’. Moreso, Section 14(8) of the NCSA stipulates that, ‘the correctional service shall take adequate steps to ensure the prevention of torture, inhuman and degrading treatment, and sexual and non-sexual violence and bullying against inmates. Consequently, inmates shall not be held in slavery or servitude, and labour carried out by inmates shall neither be of an afflictive nature or for the benefit of any correctional officer.²⁰ Similarly, by virtue of section 8(1) of the ACJA a suspect shall be accorded human treatment, having regard to his right to the dignity his person and not to subjected to any form of torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment. Again, by virtue of the provision of Section 1(a) of the Torture Act, government is under obligation to ensure that the rights of all persons, including suspects, detainees and inmates are respected at all times and that no person placed under investigation or held in custody of any person in authority shall be subjected to physical harm, force, violence, threat or intimidation or any act that impairs his freewill. Further, by virtue of the provision contained in Article 5 of the ACHPR, every individual including the inmates, shall have the right to the respect of his dignity inherent in human being, and accordingly, all forms of exploitation and degradation of man particularly, slavery, slave trade torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading punishment and treatment shall by prohibited. Furthermore, at the regional scene, the rights of the inmates in Nigeria to dignity of human person is protected by Robben Island Guidelines,²¹ Kampala Declaration²² and Arusha Declaration.²³ Thus, principle 3 of the Kampala Declaration adumbrates that inmates, ‘should have living condition which are compactable with human dignity’. In addition, Principle 4 of the Arusha Declaration places obligation on State parties to respect and protect the rights and dignity of inmates as well as to ensure compliance with national and international instruments protecting the rights of inmates.

Evidently, at the International front, the right of the inmates in Nigeria to dignity of human person is protected by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights,²⁴ International Covenant on Civil and Political

¹² O H Onyi-Ogelle and C Nwobodo, ‘A Comparative Disclosure of the Collective Right of Prisoners in Nigeria, South Africa, India and New Zealand’ [2020](4)(1) *African Journal of Law and Human Rights*, 107.

¹³ X Halili and Others, ‘Kosovo: Prison Structure, Prisoner’s Rights and the Treatment of Prisoners’ [2016] *Criminal Justice Praxis Journal of Ohio Council of Criminal Justice Education*, 2.

¹⁴ CFRN (n7) ss 17(2)(b), 34(1).

¹⁵ NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1).

¹⁶ Administration of Criminal Justice Act 2015, s 8(1).

¹⁷ Anti-Torture Act 2017, ss 1, 2.

¹⁸ African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Rectification and Enforcement Act) 1983, art 5.

¹⁹ CFRN (n7) s 34(1)(a)(b)(c).

²⁰ NCSA (n1) s 15(1).

²¹ Robben Island Guidelines and Measures for the Prohibition and Prevention Torture, Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment in Africa 2002, art 20.

²² Kampala Declaration (n4) prin 3.

²³ Arusha Declaration on Good Prison Practice in Africa 1999, prin 4.

²⁴ Universal Declaration of Human Right 1948, art 5.

Rights,²⁵ Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment,²⁶ United Nations Standard Minimum Rules,²⁷ United Nations Basic Principles²⁸ and United Nations Body of Principles.²⁹ Thus, Article 5 of the UDHR states that, ‘no one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment’. Article 10 of the ICCPR also aver that, ‘all persons deprived of their liberty shall be treated with humanity and with respect for the inherent dignity of human person’. Moreso, by the provisions contained in Article 11 of the CAT, State parties are under obligations to keep under systematic review interrogation rules, instructions, methods and practice as well as arrangements for the custody and treatment of person subjected to any form of arrest, detention or imprisonment in any territory under its jurisdiction, with a view to preventing any case of torture. Accordingly, States shall take measures to prevent acts of torture and no exceptional circumstances whatsoever may be involved as a justification for torture.³⁰ Further, Rule 1 of the UNSMR opined that all inmates, ‘shall be protected from torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment for which no circumstances whatsoever may be invoked as a justification’. Similarly, Principle 1 of the Body of Principles adumbrates that, ‘all persons under any form of detention or imprisonment shall be treated in a humane manner and with respect for the inherent dignity of human person’. Accordingly, no person under any form of detention or imprisonment shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.³¹ Again, Principle 1 of the Basic Principles opined that all inmate, ‘shall be treated with respect due to their inherent dignity and value’.

Thus, a basic minimum content of human dignity discerned that each human being possesses an intrinsic worth that should be respected and that some forms of conduct are inconsistent with respect for this intrinsic worth.³² The fact that a person has been confined to correctional centre does not mean he has lost his right to be treated as human being.³³ Accordingly, punitive measures as solitary confinement, physical violence, harassments threats and verbal intimidation or the use of shackles on inmates by law enforcement agents in carrying out their duties towards inmates amount to a violation of the inmates right to dignity of human person,³⁴ for which there can be no justification. The Court of Appeal in *Uzoukwu v Ezeonu*,³⁵ held that physical brutalization of the human person and mental torture in the sense of mental agony or mental worry amounts to the violation of the right to dignity of human person. Again, the Court of Appeal in *Peter Nemi v A. G. Lagos State*,³⁶ held that there is nothing in the provision of the constitution to suggest that even a condemned inmate may be inflicted with any form of act that may amount to torture or inhuman or degrading treatment. The Indian Supreme Court in *Shukla v Delhi Administration*,³⁷ held that inmates are persons and should be treated humanely, and that inmates in the

²⁵ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966, arts 7, 10(1)(2).

²⁶ Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment 1984, arts 12, 11, 16.

²⁷ United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners 2015, r 1, 8(d).

²⁸ United Nations Basic Principles for the Treatments of Prisoners 1990, prin 1.

²⁹ United Nations Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons Under any Form of Detention or Imprisonment 1988, prin 1, 6.

³⁰ CAT (n26) art 2(1)(2).

³¹ Body of Principles (n29) prin 6.

³² C McCrudden, ‘Human Dignity and Judicial Interpretation of Human Rights’ [2008](19)(4) *European Journal of International Law*, 723.

³³ M A Arorami, ‘Prisoners’ Rights Under Nigerian Law: Legal Pathways to Progressive Realization and Protection’ [2015](6)(1) *Afe Babalola University Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, 189.

³⁴ M A Ajomo and I E Okagbue, *Human Rights and the Administration of Criminal Justice in Nigeria* (Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies 1991) 209.

³⁵ (1991) 6 NWLR (Pt. 200) 708.

³⁶ (1996) 6 NWLR (Pt. 454) 42.

³⁷ AIR 1980 SC 1535; *Sunil Batra v Delhi Administration* AIR 1980 SC 1579.

correctional centre are to be protected from physical injury, corporal punishment, sexual assault, extortion, harassment and personal abuses. In *Sangth v State of Rajasthan*,³⁸ the Indian Supreme Court held that a person even during lawful detention is entitled to be treated with dignity befitting any other human being and the mere fact that he is under lawful detention does not mean that he can be subjected to ill-treatment. Moreso, the Zimbabwean Supreme Court in *Stephen Ncube v State*,³⁹ condemned the use of whipping as punishment and describe it as not only inherently brutal and cruel, but contrary to the traditional humanity practiced by almost the whole of the civilized world, being incompatible with the evolving standards of decency.

Consequently, the practice of keeping inmates on reduced diet, harassments, verbal intimidation, chaining, solitary confinement and so on, amounts to inhuman and degrading treatment.⁴⁰ However, there are abundant evidence of all forms of dehumanizing torture going on in correctional and detention centres in Nigeria.⁴¹ Human rights observance in respect of inmates is the dearest sphere in which Nigerian criminal justice system score lowest.⁴² Correctional centres conditions in Nigeria have the most dehumanizing and degrading effects on inmates.⁴³ Thus, maltreatment of inmates is common abuse in the Nigerian correctional centres where torture is frequent.⁴⁴ Inmates are subjected to chaining, solitary confinement, denial of food, harassment, verbal intimidation, threats, use of leg irons, shackles and forced labour.⁴⁵ Further, the United States Department of State Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labour in accessing the correctional centres condition in Nigeria reports that, 'correctional facilities has 50 percent more inmates than designed capacity. Pretrial detainees are held with convicted inmates. Authorities sometimes held female and male inmates together'.⁴⁶ It is also reported that, 'the majority of deaths relates to health problem, both pre-existing and as a result of detention conditions or treatment ... official also assault and, in some cases, torture detainees'.⁴⁷ Moreso, Amnesty International reports that, 'in some cell up to 100 inmates share a single toilet, which is often little more than a hole in the ground. In other cells buckets are used as toilets... the inadequate sanitary facilities make it virtually difficult to the inmates to maintain their dignity'.⁴⁸ Another obvious violation of the rights of the inmates to human dignity is the provision of corporal punishment in Section 359 of the NPSSO which allows the correctional authorities to inflict corporal punishment with strokes of cane on the buttocks of the inmates without clothing. The identity of the warder who inflicted the corporal punishment on the inmate is also

³⁸ AIR 1989 SC 10.

³⁹ (1987) ZLR 62 SC.

⁴⁰ T O Ifaturot, 'The Challenges of Nigerian Prisoners in the Light of the Human Rights Campaigns' [1992](3) (8-9) *Journal of Contemporary legal problems*, 116.

⁴¹ N J Udombana, 'An Examination of the Rights of Prisoners and Detainees in Nigeria' [2010](6)(1) *Nigeria Bar Journal*, 14.

⁴² C O Okonkwo, 'The Nigerian Penal System in the Light of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Right, in K U Awa and Y Osinbajo (eds), *Perspective on Human Rights* [1992](12) *Federal Ministry of Justice Law Review*, 100.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ K N Edeh and D O Anumba 'The Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners in Nigeria' [2013] (1)(1) *Journal of Current Issues in Nigeria*, 177.

⁴⁵ F E Nlerum, 'Rights of Prisoners' in O Okpara, *Human Rights Law and Practice in Nigeria I* (Publicom International Nig. Limited 2009) 238.

⁴⁶ United States Department of State Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labour, '2024 (Country Reports on Human Rights Practice',⁶ <<https://www.state.gov/report/2024-country-reports-human-right-practice-nigeria>> accessed 16 February, 2026.

⁴⁷ Australian Government Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade, '2020 Country Information Report: Nigeria', 31 <<https://www.dfat.gov.au/sites/default/files/dfat-country-information-report-nigeria>> accessed 16 February, 2026.

⁴⁸ Amnesty International, 'Nigeria: Prisoners' Rights Systematically Flouted' (Amnesty International Publication 2008) 20<<https://www.amnesty.org/art.44/001/2008/en>> accessed 16 February, 2026.

concealed from the inmate.⁴⁹ These obvious abuses contravene the rights of the inmates to dignity of human person guaranteed under the Nigerian legal instruments,⁵⁰ and other regional⁵¹ and international human rights legal instruments protecting the right of the inmates.⁵²

The right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person is parasitic. Incidental to the enjoyment of this right are certain minimum standards of treatment to which inmates are entitled.⁵³ These rights are aimed at improved correctional centres conditions befitting the status of inmates as dignified human beings.⁵⁴ Accordingly, implicit and incidental to the right of the inmates to dignity of human person are the rights to a befitting accommodation, bedding and clothing. These rights shall be examined here under.

2.1 Right to Befitting Accommodation

The right of the Nigerian inmates to a befitting accommodation implicit in the right to human dignity, is protected under the Nigerian correctional Service Act,⁵⁵ Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders⁵⁶ and United Nations Standard Minimum Rules.⁵⁷ Thus, Section 9(1)(h) of the NCSA adumbrates that:

The minister may specify the area and landmass for which the custodial centre is established, provided that in every build so declared as a custodial centre, sleeping accommodation shall meet all requirement of health with consideration given, among others to adequate floor space, water and sanitation amenities, lighting and ventilation.

Further, Section 30(3) of the NCSA there aver that, ‘shall be the provision of basic needs to meet the minimum standards for the treatment of inmates which includes accommodation. Again, Order 56 of the NPSSO opined that where possible, each inmate ‘shall be placed in a separate cell or compartment...’ Moreso, Rule 12(1) of the UNSMR opined that, “were sleeping accommodation is in individual or rooms, each inmate shall occupy by night a cell or room by himself or herself”. Accordingly, all accommodation provided for the use of inmates and in particular all sleeping accommodation shall meet all requirements of health, due regard being paid to climate condition and particularly, to cubic content of air, minimum floor space lighting, heating and ventilation.⁵⁸

The intendment of these provisions of the law of the rights of the Nigerian inmates to a befitting accommodation which is implicit to the right to dignity of human person is the provision of a comfortable accommodation to inmates in Nigeria. Thus, in *Fasehu v Attorney General of the Federation*,⁵⁹ the Court of Appeal held that the practice of keeping inmates in deplorable conditions in custody pending their trial is a glaring misinterpretation of the constitution. The court held further that the inmates are entitled to decent accommodation and environment while in custody pending the hearing and determination of their cases. However, this right has been abused severally by the correctional authorities. Thus, most Nigerian correctional centres do not have sleeping accommodation that meet all requirements for good health and in most cases, the correctional service do not provide minimum floor space and the rooms do not provide enough space for ventilation.⁶⁰ Most cells have only small windows for ventilation and those on death row

⁴⁹ Nigeria Prisons Service Standing Order 2011, ord 359(e).

⁵⁰ CFRN (n7) ss 17(2)(b), 34(1); NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1); ACJA (n16) s 8(1); Torture Act (n17) ss 1, 2; ACHPR (n18) art 5.

⁵¹ Robben Island Guidelines (n21) art 20; Kampala Declaration (n4) prin 3; Arusha Declaration (n23) prin 4.

⁵² UDHR (n24) art 5; ICCPR (n25) arts 7, 10(1)(2); CAT (n26) arts 1, 2, 11,16; UNSMR (n27) rr 1, 18(d); Basic Principles (n28) prin 1; Body of Principles (n29) prin 1, 6.

⁵³Udombana (n41) 15.

⁵⁴*Ibid.*

⁵⁵ NCSA (n1) ss 4(2)(a), 9(1)(b), 30(3).

⁵⁶ NPSSO (n49) ord 56.

⁵⁷ UNSMR (n27) r 12.

⁵⁸*Ibid.*, r 13.

⁵⁹ (2006) 4 WRN 107.

⁶⁰ Edeh (n44) 176.

are held in cells that are tiny, dark and filthy, with almost no ventilation.⁶¹ Awaiting trial inmates are generally held in much overcrowded quarters.⁶² The National Human Rights Commission reports that, ‘from the 36 prisons audited, the total capacity was 17,191 against the total lock up of 34,581’. This shows that almost all the inmates were congested.⁶³ Dambazau, reported that, there is no room for prisoners and anybody who goes into that place as a human being is coming out as an animal.⁶⁴ Thus, the right to a befitting accommodation of the Nigerian inmates in the Nigerian Correctional centres falls below the standard minimum required of a correctional service. These contravention of the right of the Nigerian inmates to a befitting accommodation guaranteed under relevant laws⁶⁵ are antithetical to the right to dignity of human person protected under the Nigerian legal instrument⁶⁶ and other regional⁶⁷ and international human right legal instruments.⁶⁸

2.2 Right to Bed/Beddings

The right of the Nigerian inmates to a comfortable bed and beddings, incidental to the right to dignity of human person, is protected under the Nigerian Correctional Service Act,⁶⁹ Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders,⁷⁰ and United Nations Standard Minimum Rules.⁷¹ Thus, Order 749 of the NPSSO aver that all inmates ‘shall be issued with a mattress, two blankets and one pillow each. Staff on inspection shall ensure that all articles of bedding are correct’. Accordingly, the Superintendent shall ensure that bedding is maintained and any defect promptly repaired.⁷² Again, Rule 21 of the UNSMR, adumbrates that every inmate ‘shall ... be provided with a separate bed and with separate and sufficient bedding which shall be clean when issued, kept in good order and changed often enough to ensure cleanliness’. Apparently, the provisions contained in the Nigerian laws,⁷³ runs contrary to the provision in the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules,⁷⁴ as provisions for accommodation and bedding were only made, without making provision for beds for inmates. Obviously, the reality on the ground in most Nigeria correctional centres is bizarre, as bed/beddings are one of the rarest commodities.⁷⁵ Oduyela, noted that, ‘closely associated with cell congestion is the absence of beds and beddings for inmates... It is reliably gathered that today, very few correctional centres have beds and where they exist, they are grossly inadequate for the population’.⁷⁶ A non-governmental organization, the prisoners’ rehabilitation and welfare action, has retorted that, ‘the best bed an inmate can hope for is the cold bare floor of his cell’.⁷⁷

⁶¹ Amnesty International (n48) 21.

⁶² *Ibid.*

⁶³ T Ojukwu and O B Agu (eds), ‘Prison Report 2018’ (National Human Rights Commission Publication 2018) 10.

⁶⁴ A Dambazau, ‘The Condition of Nigeria’s Prisons’ (The Guardian Nigeria 19 February 2018) <<https://www.theguardian.com>> accessed 17 February, 2026.

⁶⁵ NCSA (n1) ss 4(2)(a), 9(i)(b), 30(3); NPSSO (n49) s 56; UNSMR (n27) rr 12,13.

⁶⁶ CFRN (n7) ss 17(2)(b), 34(1); NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1); ACJA (n16) s 8(1); Torture Act (n17) ss 1, 2; ACHPR (n18) art 5.

⁶⁷ Robben Island Guidelines (n21) art 20; Kampala Declaration (n4) prin 3; Arusha Declaration (n23) prin 4.

⁶⁸ UDHR (n24) art 5; ICCPR (n25) arts 7, 10(1)(2); CAT (n26) arts 1, 2, 11, 16; UNSMR (n27) rr 1, 18(d); Basic Principles (n28) prin 1; Body of Principles (n29) prin 1, 6.

⁶⁹ NCSA (n1) ss 9(i)(b), 30(3).

⁷⁰ NPSSO (n49) ords 749, 750.

⁷¹ UNSMR (n27) r 21.

⁷² NPSSO (n49) ord 750.

⁷³ NCSA (n1) ss 9 (1)(b), 30(3); NPSSO (n49) ords 749, 750.

⁷⁴ UNSMR (n27) r 21.

⁷⁵ Udombana (n41) 16.

⁷⁶ S Oduyela, ‘Prison of Horror,’ <<https://www.nigerianworld.com/feature/publication/oduyela/0923/03.html>> accessed 17 February, 2026.

⁷⁷ Prisoners’ Rehabilitation and Welfare Action, ‘Penal Reform Educational Series: What the Laws Say About Prisoners (PRAWA Publications 1998) 8 <<https://www.prawa.org/publication>> accessed 17 February, 2026.

Thus, the abuse of the Nigerian inmates right to a comfortable bed and bedding, implicit in the right to dignity of human person are enormous. Inmates sleep in shifts on the floor not as human beings but as animals.⁷⁸ Inmates are subjected to sleep naked on a wet floor or a soaked blanket.⁷⁹ Amnesty international reports that:

In every correctional centre visited, the comparatively fortunate inmates showed dirty, tattered foam mattresses. Others sleep on mat. Many had nothing at all ... In Enugu prison the cells for inmates waiting trial have no bed at all. Up to 100 men and children per cell were sleeping on the bare floor.⁸⁰

Amnesty international found that inmates usually share beds or sleep on the floor due to inadequate beds and beddings.⁸¹ Besides, the National Human Rights Commission reports that, 'most detainees do not have bed as we saw a good number of them lying on mats'.⁸² The Commission found that in most of the correctional centres bed and beddings are grossly inadequate.⁸³

Evidently, the treatment of the right to bed and bedding of the Nigerian inmates, implicit in the right to dignity of human person, falls below the standard minimum required of a contemporary correction centres. These contraventions of the rights of the Nigerian inmates to bed and bedding protected under the relevant laws,⁸⁴ are antithetical to the right of the inmates to dignity of human person guaranteed under the Nigerian Laws,⁸⁵ regional⁸⁶ and international human rights legal instruments.⁸⁷

2.3 Right to Clothing

The right of the Nigerian inmates to clothing, implicit to the right of dignity of human person is protected under the Nigerian Correctional Service Act,⁸⁸ Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders⁸⁹ and United Nations Standard Minimum Rules.⁹⁰ Thus, Section 30(3) of the NCSA stipulates that, 'there shall be the provision of basic needs to meet the minimum standards for the treatment of inmates which includes... clothing'. Again, Order 287 of the NPSSO, which is similar with Rule 9(1) of the UNSMR adumbrates that every inmate, 'who is not allowed to wear his own clothing shall be provided with an outfit of clothing suitable for the climate and adequate to keep him in good health. Such clothing shall in no manner be degrading or humiliating'. Accordingly, all clothing shall be clean and kept in proper condition.⁹¹ Every inmate shall also be issued with two sets of uniforms upon admission.⁹²

Despite this provision on the protection of the right of the Nigerian inmates to clothing, implicit in the right of the inmates to dignity of human person, the Nigerian inmates have been treated with so much disdain, which falls below the standard minimum required of a contemporary correctional service. Thus,

⁷⁸ Y A Muhammed and Others 'The Right of Prisoners in Nigeria and the Role of Prisoners and Modern Penology' [2017](60) *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 74.

⁷⁹ Udombana (n41) 14.

⁸⁰ Amnesty International (n48) 22.

⁸¹ *Ibid.*

⁸² Ojukwu (n63) 10.

⁸³ *Ibid.*

⁸⁴ NCSA (n1) ss 9(i)(b), 30(3); NPSSO (n49) ords 749, 750; UNSMR (n27) r 21.

⁸⁵ CFRN (n7) ss 17(2)(b), 34(1); NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1); ACJA (n16) s 8(1); Torture Act (n17) ss 1, 2; ACHPR (n18) art 5.

⁸⁶ Robben Island Guidelines (n215) art 20; Kampala Declaration (n4) prin 3; Arusha Declaration (n23) prin 4.

⁸⁷ UDHR (n24) art 5; ICCPR (n25) arts 7, 10(1)(2); CAT (n26) arts 1, 2, 11, 16; UNSMR (n27) rr 1, 18(d); Basic Principles (n28) prin 1; Body of Principles (n29) prin 1,6.

⁸⁸ NCSA (n1) s 30(3).

⁸⁹ NPSSO (n49) ords 145, 238, 239, 287, 288, 289, 295, 764.

⁹⁰ UNSMR (n27) r 19(1)(2).

⁹¹ NPSSO (n49) ord 288; UNSMR (n27) r 19(2).

⁹² *Ibid.*, s 289.

the Prisoners' Rehabilitation and Welfare Action in accessing the correctional centre condition in Nigeria reports that, 'merely 10 percent of the correctional centre population is adequately clothed while the rest have nothing more than dirty rags and their bare skins to show for clothing.'⁹³ Mohammed and others, retorted that, "overcrowding makes difficult the provision of clothing in the adequate quantity and quality".⁹⁴ The National Human Rights Commission also reports that, 'the uniforms for the detainees in all the audited zones were inadequate, while correctional centres that have uniforms were old and obsolete'.⁹⁵ Inmates do not have uniform in the North East Zone of the Correctional Centres.⁹⁶ These obvious infractions of the rights of the Nigerian inmates to clothing protected under the relevant laws,⁹⁷ are antithetical to the rights of the inmate to dignity of human person guaranteed under the Nigerian law,⁹⁸ regional⁹⁹ and international human rights legal instrument.¹⁰⁰

3.0 CONCLUSION

The right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person is important to the whole idea of the respect for inmates' rights. The right of dignity of human person of the Nigerian inmates is a right which prohibits torture, inhuman and degrading treatment. The Nigerian inmates' rights to dignity of human person are protected under the relevant domestic,¹⁰¹ regional¹⁰² and international laws.¹⁰³ The derivatives of the right to dignity of human person of the Nigerian inmates are the right to a befitting accommodation,¹⁰⁴ bed/beddings¹⁰⁵ and clothing.¹⁰⁶

Thus, the denial of these rights implicit in the right to dignity of human person, as could be seen in several reports¹⁰⁷ amounts to the contravention of the rights of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person. The non-implementation of these derivatives in the Nigerian inmates' rights to dignity of human person has greatly affected the psyche of the inmates in Nigeria, thereby causing recidivism.

Consequently, the Nigerian authorities, particularly the Nigerian Correctional Services, National Human Rights Commission, Legal Aid Council of Nigeria among others, are endowed with the responsibility of protecting these rights and therefore should take measures in ensuring the protection of the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person and to continue to ensure the curtailment of further violation of these rights which are derivatives of the right to dignity of human person.

⁹³ PRAWA (n77) 7.

⁹⁴ Muhammed (n78) 74.

⁹⁵ Ojukwu (n63) 19.

⁹⁶ *Ibid*, 42.

⁹⁷ NCSA (n1) s 30(3); NPSSO (n49) ords 287, 288, 289; UNSMR (n27) r 19 (1)(2).

⁹⁸ CFRN (n7) ss 17(2)(b), 34(1); NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1); ACJA (n16) s 8(1); Torture Act (n17) ss 1,2; ACHPR (n18) art 5.

⁹⁹ Robben Island Guidelines (n21) art 20; Kampala Declaration (n4) Prin 3; Arusha Declaration (n23) Prin 4.

¹⁰⁰ UDHR (n24) art 5; ICCPR (n25) arts 7, 10(1)(2); CAT (n26) arts 1, 2, 11, 16; UNSMR (n27) rr 1, 18(d); Basic Principles (n28) Prin 1; Body of Principles (n29) Prin 1,6.

¹⁰¹ CFRN (n7) ss 17(2)(b), 34(1); NCSA (n1) ss 14(8), 15(1); ACJA (n16) s 8(1); Anti-Torture Act 2017, ss 1, 2; ACHPR (n18) art 5.

¹⁰² Robben Island Guidelines (n21) art 20; Kampala Declaration (n4) prin 3; Arusha Declaration (n23) prin 4.

¹⁰³ UDHR (n24) art 5; ICCPR (n25) arts 7, 10(1)(2); CAT (n26) arts 12, 11, 16; UNSMR (n27) r 1, 8(d); Basic Principles (n28) prin 1; Body of Principles (n29) prin 1, 6.

¹⁰⁴ NCSA (n1) ss 4(2)(a), 9(1)(b), 30(3); NPSSO (n49) ord 56; UNSMR (n27) r 12.

¹⁰⁵ *Ibid*, ss 9(i)(b), 30(3); NPSSO (n49) ords 749, 750; UNSMR (n27) r 21.

¹⁰⁶ *Ibid*,s 30(3); NPSSO (n49) ords 145, 238, 239, 287, 288, 289, 295, 764; UNSMR (n27) r 19(1)(2).

¹⁰⁷ United States Department of State Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labour (n46); Australian Government Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (n47); Amnesty International (n48); Ojukwu (n63); Prisoners' Rehabilitation and Welfare Action (n77).

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The Nigerian Correctional Service should treat the Nigerian inmates with measures that conforms with their rights to dignity of human person guaranteed under the Nigerian Constitution, Nigerian Correctional Service Act, Anti-Torture Act, Robben Island Guidelines and Measure for the prohibition and Prevention of Torture, Cruel, inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment in Africa, Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, United Nations Standard Minimum Rule, among others.
2. The provisions of Order 359 of the Nigerian Prisons Service Standing Orders 2011, dealing with corporal punishment, should be repeal for contravening the Nigerian inmates' rights to dignity of human person.
3. Adequate funding for the Nigerian Correctional Service should be provided in the Nigerian Appropriation laws in order to take adequate care of the Nigerian inmates' basic needs protecting their rights to dignity of human person, such as accommodation, bed/bedding, Clothing, and so on.
4. The provisions of Section 34 of the Nigerian Constitution should be amended to include 'humane condition in detention' as one of its Sub-Sections in order to protect the right of the Nigerian inmates to dignity of human person.